

On the Computability of Protein Structure and Function: Implications for Cancer Therapy, and AlphaFold

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Abstract:

Since the advent of computers, biology has been reshaped by the integration of computational tools and techniques, enabling breakthroughs in areas such as genomics, cancer therapy, and protein folding, but comparatively little attention has been given to the computational limitations of biological systems. It is shown here that many diseases related to protein folding, or management of the cell cycle can be understood as biological “halting problems”. That is, they belong to a special class of computational problems that are said to be uncomputable and are demonstrable limitations of biological systems as well. This argument is supported by three points. First, linear organic polymers are countably infinite in sequence, but uncountably infinite in structure. Second, polymers like DNA, RNA, and proteins are trivially capable of sufficiently expressive interactions. Third, if a protein structure or activity is dependent on an uncomputable problem, then the protein structure or activity is also uncomputable. The implication is that biological organisms can offer only greedy solutions to complex problems and that some common diseases like cancer are a natural consequence of computer theory.

Axiom	A foundational assumption or fundamental rule in a mathematical system.
Completeness	The property of a set of axioms that all true statements can be proven true.
Computability	The property that a given problem can be solved by a Turing Machine.
Consistency	The property of a set of axioms that there are no contradictions.
Countability	Able to be counted; Equal to or smaller than the set of Natural Numbers.
Decidability	The property that a set of axioms always provide a “yes” or “no” answer to “yes” or “no” questions.
Halting Problem	Determine if a computer will loop forever or halt on an arbitrary program.
Natural Number	Any whole number greater than or equal to 0.
Peano's Axioms	Elementary axioms of arithmetic and natural numbers.
Recursive	The property that a definition is self-referential.
Real Number	Any of a continuous range of values that can be defined with a number line.
Turing Machine	An abstract computational device capable of executing any arithmetic algorithm.

Introduction:

The Limits of Computation

The limitations of computation were first presented by Alan Turing in 1936. This work drew heavily from Kurt Gödel's Incompleteness Theorems, and together they form the foundation of modern computer theory. Their results rely on the fact that some paradoxical statements emerge from self-reference and have no logical solution. Such statements are constructed in the style of the liar's paradox (e.g., "this statement is false") and are said to be "undecidable" in systems for which they are defined¹⁻⁴. Self-referential statements are necessary for modern computers, but also impose limitations on the resulting system. These limitations can be summarized with three terms:

- **Completeness** is the property that all true statements can be proven true.
- **Consistency** is the property that no false statements can be proven true.
- **Computability** is the property that a given problem can be solved by a Turing Machine.

Kurt Gödel showed that if a mathematical statement asserts its own unprovability (e.g., "This statement is not provable"), then the system in which it is defined may be complete or consistent, but not both. This is because having a proof of a statement that asserts itself to be unprovable is an inconsistency. The alternative is being unable to prove a true statement, which would mean the system is incomplete. Gödel's first incompleteness theorem refers to the result that no formal system capable of self-reference can be both complete and consistent. The related result that no system can confirm its own consistency is commonly referred to as Gödel's second incompleteness theorem⁵⁻⁸.

Alan Turing extended Gödel's reasoning to examine the limitations of machines that automate the process of performing calculations. Turing showed that a machine made to compute proofs of mathematical statements must be unable to provide a correct result for unprovable conjectures. That is, a solution to an undecidable problem must be uncomputable. To do this, Turing introduced what is now called the "halting problem," which aims to determine the halting behavior of a Turing machine. The halting problem is uncomputable, and a proof emerges when a computer is tasked with predicting the halting behavior of itself (e.g., "Halt if this program never halts"). Everyday computer users may be familiar with this problem as a "freezing" behavior which requires the user to either restart a given task, or wait to see if the machine will finish. The probability that an arbitrary computer will complete a given task (halt), or loop forever, is an example of an uncomputable number, and is known as "Chaitin's Constant"^{9,10}.

Can Machines Think?

A seemingly obvious result of Gödel's incompleteness theorems is the understanding that the human mind must somehow go beyond what is computable by machines. John Lucas and Roger Penrose separately argued that simply by demonstrating any limitation of mathematics, Kurt Gödel proved his mind (and the minds of other mathematicians) can see inherent truths about the universe that are inaccessible to machines^{7,8,11,12}. Alan Turing believed the fallacy in this line of reasoning to be that it assumes the human mind has no Gödelian paradox of its own. Turing further argued that the very question of "can machines think?" was "too meaningless to deserve discussion" and recommended researchers instead focus on engineering intelligent machines^{3,13,14}. The now seminal work "Computing Machinery and Intelligence" introduced the *imitation game* (commonly known as the "Turing Test"), which framed the discussion around whether or not a question-and-answer machine could fool a human interrogator about being a machine³. In so doing, Turing dismissed the problem of "can machines think?" and laid the groundwork for the eventual field of Artificial Intelligence^{3,13,15,16}.

Biological Halting Problems

For the last 75 years, the conversation about computer intelligence has been dominated by the imitation game, but with rapid advancements in machine intelligence and robotics, the ascendant question becomes: “*Can organisms do things impossible for machines?*”. By refocusing on the limitations of biological systems and what they cannot do, the problem of “can machines think?” flips on itself and challenges biology to solve a problem known to be unsolvable by machines†. Because if organisms cannot do things impossible for machines, then it follows that machines can be built to think. Therefore, the mission here is to understand how computational structures emerge from biological systems, then show that cells inherit the computational limitations of machines. The main argument consists of 7 propositions. Propositions I-III demonstrate the Turing Completeness of life’s core molecules: DNA, RNA, and especially proteins. Proposition IV demonstrates that protein structures are uncountable. Propositions V-VI show that the cell cycle is a biological halting problem, meaning that cancer is a necessary risk for multicellular life. Finally, proposition VII demonstrates that some protein structures are uncomputable.

† *Others have previously suggested there may exist biological halting problems. See Neumann 2021*¹⁷, *Hofstadter 1979*⁵, *Turing 1950*³.

Background

Gödel Numbering and Isomorphism

The heart of Gödel’s proof is a technique called Gödel numbering, which encodes mathematical expressions as natural numbers. It is a special trick that allows the construction of self-referential paradoxes that are undecidable. In the parlance of mathematics, a formal system is a set of symbols and rules that allow one to construct logical or mathematical expressions for evaluation. The fundamental rules of a formal system are called “axioms”, and subsequently derived true expressions are called “theorems”. Peano’s Axioms are used to define natural numbers. In modern form, there are only 5 axioms, but they are powerful enough to define much of modern mathematics^{1,18,19}. When combined with Gödel numbering, they are expressive enough to perform any operation a computer can perform²⁰. Below is a typical formulation of the Peano Axioms:¹⁹

- I. 0 is a number.
- II. If n is a number, then so is the successor of n (commonly taken as $n+1$)
- III. 0 is not a successor of any number
- IV. If two numbers have the same successor, then they are equal.
- V. The inductive axiom: If a property holds for “ n ” and “ $n+1$ ”, then the property holds for all numbers.

The Peano Axioms start with an initial natural number, usually taken to be 0. Next, a successor function “S” is defined, which gives a unique “successor” natural number for each natural number input. (thus, natural numbers can be written as: 0, S(0), SS(0), SSS(0) ...). “Peano Arithmetic” adds to Peano’s Axioms, arithmetic operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, etc.) and operations of first order logic (includes “and”, “or”, “not”, as well as existential (\exists) and universal (\forall) quantifiers). It is with these tools that Kurt Gödel constructed a mathematical expression in the style of “This statement is unprovable.”

Gödel’s trick was to use familiar Arabic numerals to represent the axioms & symbols of Peano Arithmetic (Table 2) and was done in such a way that all constructed statements (be they true or false) would also correspond to a unique natural number. An Arabic numeral used in Gödel numbering is called “number sign”, and a formula composed of number signs is called a “class-sign”. The first 7 number signs were given by Gödel (odd numbers 1-13 below), while the remaining symbols were left to the reader to assign. To conserve the ordering of symbols, one takes the first symbol and makes it a power of the lowest prime number. This is repeated for the second symbol, which is made to be the power of the next lowest prime

number, and continues for each number sign: (e.g., $2^h * 3^i * 5^j * 7^k * 11^l$; where h, i, j, k, l are class signs). Since the exact mapping of symbols to numbers does not matter, this construction jumps ahead immediately to assign those symbols Gödel used to show that some statements are undecidable:

number-sign	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	...
symbol	0	S	¬	∨	∀	()	r	Z	Gen	...

Where " x Gen y " is the generalization of the variable " x " on the class-sign " y ", " Z " is a number sign for a given number, and " r " is a class-sign such that neither " x Gen r " nor its negation, " $Neg(x$ Gen $r)$ ", is a consequence of the axioms of Peano arithmetic. Then the class-sign for " Z Gen r " is precisely:

$$(1) \quad 2^{17} 3^{19} 5^{15} = 4.649045868 \times 10^{24}$$

Gödel numbering is an example of isomorphism, which is a special mapping between structurally similar sets that preserves information about how set members are related^{5,21,22}. By assigning the symbols of Peano arithmetic to natural numbers represented with Arabic numerals, it is possible to encode mathematical statements as Arabic numerals, which can easily be decoded back to Peano arithmetic. Isomorphism is an essential component of computational systems because if mechanical systems are to compute anything, they must have symbols or states that induce some meaning for the operator. Isomorphism, therefore, is a kind of emergent meaning that applies to some pairs of sets and is essential for Gödel's proof.

Incompleteness Theorems and the Halting Problem

Theorems are true statements derived from axioms or other theorems. The statement: "*if 'a' and 'b' are natural numbers, then there exists another natural number 'c' such that 'a+b=c'*", is a theorem of Peano Arithmetic. By combining axioms or other existing theorems, it is always possible to derive a new theorem (e.g., " $a+b = c$ " can be used to show that " $a+b+c = 2c$ "). This process is easy enough that one might hope to build a program that automatically generates new theorems, just to see if it proves a given proposition. Such a program would be recursive since it examines its own list of rules to generate new rules. Therefore, this program is given the name "RecursiveProofLibrary". If the RecursiveProofLibrary is a library of all provable theorems of the Peano Axioms, then the library must be incomplete as long as it is also free of contradictions. That is, there must be true statements of Peano arithmetic not included in the RecursiveProofLibrary.

One possible consequence of a Gödel statement given to a computer is the halting problem. Consider a function "*Bew*" which accepts a statement as an argument and decides if it is a provable theorem. Next, suppose that a given argument " t " states something to the effect of "*I am not provable by the axioms of *this* system.*" It follows that there can be no proof " p " for theorem " t " because that would be a contradiction. The alternate case is that " p " does not prove " t ", which means the program must select another proof from the test, the next proof " p ," and check if that proves " t ". Since new proofs can always be derived, it follows that the RecursiveProofLibrary can never be exhausted, therefore, no guarantee can be made that it will stop. A consistent implementation loops forever because there is no proof " p " for " t ", even though " t " is a true statement. If there exists an unprovable true statement, then the system is *incomplete*. Finally, the inability to determine if the function "*Bew*" will halt or not is known as the Halting Problem.

Box 1: Proof sketch of the Halting Problem and Gödel's First Incompleteness Theorem:

Let the theorem "t" be a statement that asserts its own unprovability. If "Bew" is a function that determines if the theorem is true, then it cannot prove "t" true (since that would be a contradiction of "t"), and the function "Bew" will never halt because the *RecursiveProofLibrary* is endless. Since "t" is true and unprovable, "Bew" is incomplete.

```
function Bew(theorem t)
  for each proof "p" in RecursiveProofLibrary:
    if "p" proves "t":
      return true
```

Avoiding Gödelian Paradoxes

There are many ways one might hope to avoid paradoxes of self-reference. Gödel's "second incompleteness theorem" shows why this is not allowed. This theorem states that no paradox-inducing system can affirm its own consistency. Some may take this to mean that paradoxes of self-reference *are* resolvable, provided one just uses a better system. Unfortunately, this strategy of "passing the buck" is necessarily circular since any imagined system that proves the consistency of an existing system must also bear the burden of needing to be proved consistent. This, in turn, requires yet a third system, still not known to be consistent. In this way, paradoxes of self-reference tend to confound efforts to contain them⁵. Even quantum computers cannot be relied on to solve paradoxes of self-reference in Turing machines. A known Gödelian paradox of quantum mechanics relates to the spectral gap problem, a solution to which would allow the rapid discovery of materials suitable for superconductors and quantum computers²³.

The only effective practice offered here is the use of greedy algorithms to handle undecidable problems with fractional efficacy. All real-world digital computers are subject to failure, and it follows from the halting problem that it is not possible to predict with certainty if a system will recover. In computer networks, the term "high availability" refers to a computer system that is available to users with 99.999% reliability, meaning such a system would be allowed only 5 minutes of continuous downtime per year^{24,25}. This level of availability can reasonably be achieved through the dedication of more computers to monitor and manage mission-critical computer systems, but the fundamental problems of undecidability, in this case, the halting problem, never go away²⁵⁻²⁸.

Primary Structure

(Ser-Trp-Thr-Trp-Glu-Gly-Asn-Lys-Trp-Thr-Trp-Lys)

Secondary Structure

(top) α -helix,
(bottom) extended strands

Tertiary Structure

CFTR membrane protein

Quaternary Structure

p53 tetramer complex with DNA

Disordered Structure

Multiple structures of the binding domain of p53: (top) single structure, (bottom) 20 structures

Figure 1: Primary Structure: Peptide sequence of a tryptophan zipper²⁹. Secondary Structure: (top) 23 amino acid α -helix³⁰ (bottom) β -hairpin with loop and extended strands depicted as vertical arrows (13 amino acids)²⁹. Tertiary Structure: cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (1,441 amino acids)³¹. Quaternary structure: p53 tetramerization structure with DNA³². Disordered Structure: MDM2 binding domain shown by itself (Top) and with Multiple solved structures overlaid (Bottom)³³.

Protein Structure

There are four different levels of protein structure. Primary Structure refers to the sequence of amino acids of a protein or peptide and is defined by the sequence of nucleotides in an mRNA transcript. Secondary Structure emerges from hydrogen bonding of the protein backbone³⁴. Common examples include helices, loops, turns, and “extended strands,” which commonly form beta sheets³⁵. Tertiary Structure emerges from hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions of amino acid side chains³⁶. Globular proteins have a well-defined structure and copious hydrophobic amino acids that form the core of the globular protein domains, while hydrophilic amino acids orient outward where they interact with other hydrophilic molecules and water. Quaternary Structure refers to complexes of protein or proteins and nucleotides. Quaternary structures can also include nucleotide-protein complexes like the p53 tetramer and DNA^{32,37} (Figure 1) or much larger structures like ribosomes, or amyloid plaques associated with Alzheimer’s Disease³⁸.

While many proteins can be shown to fold into stable three-dimensional structures on their own, not all proteins form stable structures. Disordered Structures are those that lack a stable secondary or tertiary structure (Figure 1; Disordered structure). Proteins that are particularly enriched for disorder are called “intrinsically disordered proteins” (IDPs). They are characterized by domain-sized unstructured regions that undergo a reversible change in structure, often resulting from interacting with a target (Figure 1; Quaternary structure). While disordered proteins may assume different shapes, many disordered regions still exhibit flexibility in the bound state, and it is believed that this structural flexibility enables target promiscuity³⁹. It is estimated that more than 30% of the human proteome may be unstructured regions⁴⁰. Thus, disordered structures are an integral part of cellular functions.

Structure prediction and AlphaFold

The “protein folding problem” refers to the challenge of predicting a protein's structure from its sequence of amino acids alone. This problem is sometimes described as the “holy grail” of computational biology^{41–43} because an efficient solution to this problem promises to unlock advancements in medicine^{43–46}, drug discovery,⁴³ and synthetic biology^{47–49}. The protein folding problem is widely assumed to be “NP-Complete”,⁵⁰ meaning it should be possible to guess and verify any protein structure. This interpretation is supported by the commonly held view in biochemistry that the expected structure of a protein should always minimize global free energy⁵⁰. While NP-Complete problems are not easy, they do come with the guarantee that a correct and computable answer exists.

Protein structure prediction generally follows two common avenues. “Template-free” algorithms rely on thermodynamic principles but are generally considered unreliable for sequences greater than 150 amino acids⁵¹ and even with shorter sequences, template-free modeling may only correctly place 30% of amino acids within a few angstroms of its correct position^{51,52}. Homology modeling is an alternative approach that assumes proteins related by evolutionary ancestry will have similar amino-acid sequences and similar structures too. By the 1980s, researchers used experimentally solved structures to inform structure predictions, achieved with greater success than template-free modeling^{53,54}. Today, homology modeling has largely given way to deep learning approaches, which still rely on solved structures and, for this review, are still considered homology modeling.

AlphaFold debuted in 2018⁵⁵ and quickly gained fame when, at the 13th biennial Critical Assessment of Protein Structure Prediction (CASP) competition, it won by such a large margin that it became the new standard in protein structure prediction^{40,55}. AlphaFold has since made available more than 214 million predicted protein sequences⁵⁶, but unfortunately suffers some of the shortcomings of its predecessors. It is largely restricted to predicting static structures and exhibits large errors in intrinsically disordered regions⁵⁷. It has difficulty predicting disease structures^{44,45}, understanding the impact of amino-acid substitutions on larger protein domains^{58,59}, and is subject to making major stereochemistry violations in

protein-nucleotide binding sites hundreds of nucleotides long⁵⁷. For these reasons, AlphaFold is still criticized for not understanding well enough the energy landscape of protein folding^{57,60,61}.

Main Methods

Proposition I: Linear polymers like DNA, RNA, and proteins have countable sequences.

DNA, RNA, and proteins are linear polymers, meaning they form from the sequential linking together of molecular subunits, called monomers, into non-branching chains⁶². Many synthetic plastics are also linear polymers, including polyvinyl chloride, which is synthesized from vinyl chloride monomers⁶³. Linear polymers are special because, as long as a linear chain has a finite number of allowed monomer types, there are only as many different polymer sequences as there are natural numbers. That is, the set of all possible linear polymers of that type is **countably infinite**. Formally, this can be proven by demonstrating that there is a bijection between natural numbers and polymer sequences (supplemental materials: Bijection of Natural Numbers to Polymers), but this fact is easier to recognize by thinking of a sequence of nucleotides or amino acids as part of an alternate numbering system. The common decimal system consists of ten symbols (0-9) but can easily be replaced by any set of countably finite symbols (Table 3: Examples of counting sets). RNA and DNA, consisting of only four nucleotides, are therefore like a base-four coding system for natural numbers. Similarly, most organisms use approximately 20 amino acids, therefore, proteins can be thought of as a base-20 numbering system made of amino acids.

Table 3: Examples of counting sets					
Decimals (base-10)	Octals (base-8)	Binary (base-2)	Nucleotides (base-4)	Amino Acids (base-20)	Peano Numbers
0	0	00000	A	A	0
1	1	00001	C	C	S(0)
2	2	00010	G	D	SS(0)
3	3	00011	U	E	SSS(0)
4	4	00100	AA	F	SSSS(0)
5	5	00101	AC	G	SSSSS(0)
6	6	00110	AG	H	SSSSSS(0)
7	7	00111	AU	I	SSSSSSS(0)
8	10	01000	CA	K	SSSSSSSS(0)
9	11	01001	CC	L	SSSSSSSSS(0)
...

Proposition II: Countability and Isomorphism allow DNA, RNA, and proteins to form computational structures.

There are numerous examples of chemical "Turing Machines" made with DNA, RNA, and Proteins. Examples include artificial control circuitry engineered with DNA using strand displacement ⁶⁴, and protein logic gates mediated entirely by protein-protein interactions ⁶⁵. Of course, it does not follow that these molecules form computational structures within cells. The theory presented here is that DNA, RNA, and proteins realize computational structures with countable sequences and isomorphic relations in the form of structural and chemical interactions of those sequences.

For the special case of linear polymers with only one monomer type, it is possible to use linear polymers to walk through Gödel's proof directly. This is because the process of polymerization is loosely described by the Peano Axioms (supplemental materials: Peano-style axioms for polymers). Such a construction would differ from the behavior of naturally occurring DNA, RNA, and proteins in that distinct polymer sequences have to be assigned initial values while the specific properties of DNA, RNA, and proteins are emergent. While this approach is entirely impractical, it has the benefit of illustrating that linear polymers realize emergent computational systems with indexable functions (thus requiring both countability and isomorphism).

Since plastic monomer precursors react to form polymer chains, one can similarly represent every natural number with a quantity of reacted or unreacted monomers letting 0 be no monomers and "n" being the total number of monomers needed to synthesize a piece of plastic. "n" can be calculated by dividing the mass of a plastic piece by the molar mass of a reacted monomer. The common industrial plastic known as PVC (poly-vinyl chloride) is synthesized from monomers of vinyl chloride (VC). VC is nice because its mass does not change when it reacts to form larger polymers (some polymers have reaction byproducts). The goal is to exploit the fact that plastic polymers like PVC form chains of monomers and that the number of monomers used is proportional to the mass of the synthesized plastic. As long as one can precisely measure the mass of some resulting blob of plastic, they can reverse engineer it as a statement by calculating the moles of monomers used, then finding its prime factorization.

The value of the class-sign of "*Z Gen r*" was previously determined to be $2^{17} 3^{19} 5^{15}$ (equation 1). Separating these multipliers:

$$\begin{aligned} (2) \quad 5^{15} &= 30,517,578,125 \cong 3.05175 \times 10^{10} \\ (3) \quad 3^{19} &= 1,162,261,467 \cong 1.16226 \times 10^9 \\ (4) \quad 2^{17} &= 131,072 \cong 1.31072 \times 10^5 \end{aligned}$$

So, for the statement *Z gen r*, is the product:

$$(5) \quad 2^{17} \cdot 3^{19} \cdot 5^{15} = 4.649045868 \times 10^{24}$$

Which would require 7.71992 moles of precursor monomers to synthesize:

$$\begin{aligned} (6) \quad 1 \text{ mol} &= 6.02214076 \times 10^{23} \\ (7) \quad N_m &\cong 4.649045 \times 10^{24} \text{ monomers} = 7.719921 \text{ mol} \end{aligned}$$

Finally, calculating the mass of a completed reaction is given by:

$$(8) \quad P = N_m \times M(x)$$

Where P is the expected mass of the synthesized polymer, $M(x)$ is the fraction of mass conserved by a reaction.

Proposition III: Minimotifs modify protein structure and behavior.

The diversity of protein-protein interactions within a cell is best exemplified by *minimotifs*, which are 2-15 amino acid long segments of proteins that are targets and signals of protein-protein interactions. There are hundreds of distinct minimotif activities,⁶⁶ and many are known to affect protein structure⁶⁷. They are important for signal transduction and can be used to represent logic gates⁶⁸. Three minimotifs of particular interest include phosphorylation, proteolysis, and binding motifs^{67,69,70}.

Phosphorylation is a modification that imparts a strong negative charge to a side chain. Amino acids like Serine, Threonine, and Tyrosine are moderately hydrophilic or moderately hydrophobic in the case of Tyrosine. The attachment of a phosphate group to any of these amino acids makes these amino acids highly hydrophilic, causing a conformational change to the protein structure^{67,69}. For example, phosphorylation of certain p53 motifs leads to tumor suppression and apoptosis^{71,72}. Another example is given by the membrane protein known as the Sodium-Potassium Pump, which relies on the attachment and removal of phosphates to induce the conformational shift required to move sodium and potassium across the cell membrane in opposite directions⁷³ – an essential activity for neuronal and muscular activation⁷⁴.

Proteolysis is a process where an amino acid sequence is cut to form two smaller sequences⁶⁹. Many proteins have regulatory regions that block the activity of a protein until it is ready to activate. Proteins that perform proteolysis are called proteases. The textbook example of proteolysis is the mammalian blood clotting cascade, where a network of inactive proteases can be rapidly activated to form blood clots⁷⁵.

Binding Motifs are special peptide sequences that facilitate the reversible sticking together of proteins^{69,76}. While binding minimotifs are common, they appear to be especially valuable for IDPs, which are known for their diverse interactions and variable structures^{67,77}. The tumor suppressor p53 is a transcription factor, meaning it helps regulate gene expression. It is also disordered, meaning it undergoes a disorder-to-order transformation upon binding to one of its targets. When p53 finds a target protein binding partner, the binding region assumes temporary tertiary structures⁷⁸. Mutations in the TP53 gene are commonly implicated in cancer⁷⁹, and p53 mutants lacking proline-rich binding motifs have a severely reduced capacity to induce apoptosis⁷⁷.

Proposition IV: Protein structures are uncountable.

It is shown here that the diagonalization method, which proves real numbers are not countable, can also be used to show that protein structures are not countable either. The method of diagonalization is an example of proof by contradiction, meaning one is permitted to assume a counter proposition to demonstrate it leads to an impossibility. The assumption examined here is the widely held view that the protein folding problem is NP-complete, which entails that all proteins have a computable “best” structure. That is, every protein has a singular ideal structure that is determined by the protein sequence. According to proposition I, protein sequences are countable, therefore, protein structures must also be countable if every protein has a “best” structure. The application of the diagonalization method requires encoding each protein sequence and structure as a real number. The procedure chosen here is to combine the sequence encoding described in proposition I with a decimal expansion of arbitrary precision to define the protein structure. Thus, a real number encoding that represents a protein sequence and its “best” structure will be of the form:

$$(9) \quad \text{encoding} = \text{sequence}.\text{structure}$$

Let A be the encoding of a protein, and let Π and Γ represent the sequence and structure of A such that:

$$(10) \Lambda = \Pi + \Gamma = \Pi.\Gamma$$

Figure 2: φ , ψ , and ω bond rotations of a peptide chain.

For this demonstration, a protein structure is described by quantifying the rotations made along the polymer backbone. Each amino acid has three molecular bonds that contribute to the backbone. They are labeled φ , ψ , and ω bonds in Figure 2. Each bond position is divided into 10 macro positions that can be represented by one position of the decimal expansion. To allow for arbitrary precision of protein structure, an infinite decimal expansion is allowed to define the protein backbone, which specifies the different φ , ψ , and ω bonds. Let Π be a natural number representing a protein sequence as shown in proposition I. Let “n” be the number of amino acids in Π , and let Φ , Ψ , and Ω be sets that contain all φ , ψ , and ω bond angles, respectively, in the structure of Π :

$$(11) \Phi = \{\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3, \dots, \varphi_n\}$$

$$(12) \Psi = \{\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3, \dots, \psi_n\}$$

$$(13) \Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n\}$$

The next step is to encode all φ , ψ , and ω rotations of amino acids in Π as a real number Γ , such that: $0 \leq \Gamma < 1$. Let φ_a be a sequence of numbers representing the first decimal position of each angle of each φ bond. Similarly, let φ_b represent the symbol at the second decimal position for each φ bond in Π and let φ_c be the third. Then the decimal expansion Γ is:

$$(14) \Gamma = \varphi_a \psi_a \omega_a \varphi_b \psi_b \omega_b \varphi_c \psi_c \omega_c \varphi_d \psi_d \omega_d \dots$$

According to proposition III, the structure of some proteins is affected by interactions with other proteins. Therefore, there must be some protein structures not included on the list. If there were only a few cases where proteins modify each other's structure, one might conclude that protein structures are still countable (as demonstrated by Hilbert's Infinite Hotel). Unfortunately, since protein-protein interactions are the norm, not the exception, it is necessary to also consider potentially infinite protein-protein interactions when considering a set of infinite possible proteins. Let Π_n be the number sign for a natural

number that represents the n^{th} protein sequence as defined in proposition I. Let Γ_n be the number sign for the decimal expansion that represents the n^{th} structure as defined in proposition IV. Then, every protein has a unique number that defines both its sequence and structure. If protein sequences are countable, then all proteins can be listed like so:

$$(15) \Lambda_n = \Pi_n \cdot \Gamma_n = L(\text{sequence} = \Pi_n, \text{other_sequences} = \{\Pi_a, \Pi_a, \Pi_a, \Pi_b, \Pi_b, \dots\})$$

L is a function of natural numbers since it only requires a list of protein sequences to determine a structure, and Λ is a real number output of L that represents the protein sequence and structure. Let **other_sequences[]** be an arbitrary set of protein sequences Π_n interacts with.

The powerset of a set S, P(S), is the set of all proper subsets of S (a proper subset is a set without repeats). According to set theory, the cardinality of the powerset of an infinite set is greater than the cardinality of the set S and is given by $P(S) = 2^S$ ⁸⁰. Therefore, if one were to enumerate all possible resulting structures based on possible protein-protein interactions, then the set of resulting possible structures is of the same cardinality as real numbers:

$$(16) P|\mathbb{N}| = 2^{\aleph_0} = |\mathbb{R}|$$

So even if one ignores the fluid motion of proteins and assumes proteins have a computable best structure, the larger set of possible protein complexes is uncountable, and from this it follows immediately that some elements within that set are uncomputable². Critics may correctly point out that not all proteins will form stable structures and, therefore, should not be assumed to form complexes. On these grounds, they may feel inclined to reject the application of the diagonalization method as described above, but just because a protein does not form a stable structure on its own does not mean it does not form a stable structure with other proteins. Furthermore, if one is to insist that some combinations of proteins will form no stable structure at all, then they have already conceded that protein structures are uncountable.

Proposition V: Some Cells Signal their internal state via MHC class I antigen presentation.

Antigen presentation is a process by which cells display fragments of degraded proteins on their surface, and is relied upon by vertebrates for self-identification and recognition of cells that are potentially infected or cancerous. As part of normal cellular activity, proteins are continuously recycled, and MHC class I antigen presentation is the process by which some cells display fragments of degraded proteins for evaluation by the host immune system⁸¹. Proteins marked for degradation are broken down by the 26S proteasome^{82,83}, and fragments that are 8 or 9 amino acids long, with hydrophobic or alkaline C-terminal amino acids, are eligible for display by the MHC I complex⁸⁴. Host immune cells meticulously check peptides displayed by cells, looking for non-host structures. When CD8+ T cells encounter an unrecognized protein structure displayed by the loaded MHC I complex, such as somatic mutations or viral proteins, they respond by attacking the offending cell⁸⁵.

The importance of the Major Histocompatibility Complex for vertebrate immune systems is apparent when examining organisms with dysfunctional proteins involved in antigen presentation. MHC I knockouts in mice severely hamper immune response⁸⁶ and provoke attacks from NK cells, which expect MHC proteins as proof of self signals⁸⁷⁻⁸⁹, while combined knockouts of MHC I/II and T-Cell receptors produce rodents highly amenable to tissue grafts^{90,91}. One major limitation of antigen presentation however is that some protein fragments are not eligible for display. Therefore, MHC class I antigen presentation is an important but greedy algorithm for self-identification and cell-health signaling.

Results

Proposition VI: If the cell cycle is a program that loops, then there exists a protein whose structure best represents the cell's halting probability.

Mammalian cells produce some 10,000 distinct protein sequences⁹². The average length of eukaryotic proteins is >450 amino acids and appears to follow a “log normal” distribution⁹³. Therefore, most gene-expressing mammalian tissues can reasonably select from millions of distinct protein fragments for antigen presentation. According to proposition IV, every protein or peptide structure can be encoded with the decimal expansion Γ , and by definition, the probability of some event is a value between zero and one. Therefore, it is a matter of logical necessity that there exists a protein or peptide whose structure is closest to the cell's halting probability. While the encoding system used in proposition IV would be invalid in living cells, proposition V describes a process by which cells signal their internal state using discarded protein fragments. As long as some peptides signal to the immune system that there is a problem while others do not, the proposition that there exists a protein whose structure best represents the cell's halting probability still holds.

Proposition VII: The structures of some proteins are uncomputable by machines and unrecognizable by cells.

If there is a protein structure that corresponds to the probability that a machine will halt, then that protein structure must be uncomputable⁹. According to proposition VI, a cell must have a structure that best represents its halting probability, but such a structure is necessarily uncomputable for a Turing machine since it would be a solution to the Halting Problem – a finding corroborated by the fact that proteins are empirically sufficiently expressive to form computational systems (proposition II) and protein structures are regularly modified as part of normal protein function (proposition III). Since the halting probability is an uncomputable problem for any computational system, it follows that the halting problem is uncomputable for polymer automata as well. Or put more simply: since the halting probability is uncomputable, so is deciding which protein to display. Therefore, there is no guarantee a computer can correctly predict a protein structure, and no guarantee immune cells will correctly recognize a peptide associated with oncogenic activity.

Discussion

Decidability in Biological Systems

These results show that the immense complexity of cells do not contradict a computational model of life; rather, understanding the complexity of life stands to benefit from a more direct application of computer theory to biology. The fact that computational undecidability emerges from self-reference and indexability of functions means that biological systems are trivially capable of realizing computational structures. This does require a concession, however, that many problems in biology have no computable solution. Therefore, these results may come as somewhat of a vindication of holism.

These results also offer new insights into what Gödelian undecidability means for natural systems, including what could reasonably be expected from a “theory of everything.” This is because if biological systems are assumed to emerge from physical principles, then it follows that any theory of physics complete enough to explain biological systems is necessarily incomplete or self-contradictory. For example, according to proposition VI, every cell has a peptide fragment that best represents the cell's halting probability. Even if that peptide has a definite and easy-to-determine structure, the problem of “which peptide best indicates a cell's halting probability?” has no general solution.

These results should not be used to support arguments by Penrose ^{7,8}, Lucas ¹¹, and others that “consciousness is uncomputable” or that “machines cannot think”. Quite the opposite, the failure of biological systems to rout out the halting problem, or make themselves immune to diseases of protein folding, is evidence that even complex biological systems are constrained by paradoxes of self-reference. Therefore, it is not sufficient to congratulate oneself for mastering Peano arithmetic and assume supremacy of the mind over machines. Proving human intelligence cannot be replicated by machines means proving the human mind has no paradox of self reference, and given the difficult nature of paradoxes, it is presumptuous to assume all paradoxes can be recognized and evaluated by a human.

Cancer as a Biological Halting Problem

For the last 25 years, the dominant view of cancer has been that different cancers have common characteristics that can be targeted to affect a broad class of cancer types. This is commonly referred to as the “Hallmarks of Cancer”. It originally described six common characteristics of cancer: “evading apoptosis”, “self-sufficiency in growth signals”, “Insensitivity to anti-growth signals”, “sustained angiogenesis”, “tissue invasion and metastasis”, and “limitless replicative potential” ⁹⁴. In 2011, two more hallmarks were added,⁹⁵ and as of 2022, there are up to 14 hallmarks of cancer⁹⁶ – with each generation more granular than the next. The understanding that cancer is a biological halting problem is an advancement over Hallmarks because it replaces a potentially never ending list of cancer characteristics with a fundamental understanding that if the cell cycle is a program that loops, then the Halting Problem implies no decision procedure can be guaranteed to correctly determine if a cell cycle will halt. Further, it points to potential iterative approaches to targeting different kinds of cancer.

Figure 3. Programmable anti-cancer therapy. The proteins Ras, Src, and p53 are commonly found mutated in cancer and are targets of existing cancer treatments. If there is an efficient way to computationally determine a protein structure and interactions, then it should be possible to select a protein that interacts with specific oncogenic proteins. The imaginary protein Transducer of Oncogenic Signaling (TOS) is engineered to trigger p53-mediated apoptosis in the presence of oncogenic signaling from mutant Ras. Since proteins can have multiple functions, TOS can also block the activity of mutant p53 (mut-p53) and MDM2, which both work to suppress p53-mediated apoptosis.

Universal Tumor Killer?

Cancer is ubiquitous in multicellular life⁹⁷ and appears even in species known for their resistance to cancer, like whales⁹⁸ and naked mole-rats^{99,100}. Common medical interventions like radiation therapy and chemotherapy are effective but greedy solutions because they broadly attack all replicating cells¹⁰¹ and bear a significant risk of introducing new forms of cancer¹⁰². Therefore, a major goal of 21st-century medicine is to target cancer cells specifically. One promising approach works by leveraging the host immune system to target cancer cells. CAR-T therapy engineers a patient's immune cells to recognize surface proteins that are specific to target cancer cells¹⁰³. It leverages “cytotoxic T-cells” that kill target cells by recognizing surface antigens and releasing toxic molecules like perforin and granzymes. These proteins penetrate the target cell membrane, triggering programmed cell death (apoptosis) in the offending cell¹⁰⁴. Unfortunately, it is unlikely that CAR-T cell therapy will manifest as a universal treatment for cancer. One of the problems with CAR-T cell therapy is that cancer cells are capable of interfering with antigen recognition by downregulating expression of surface proteins (thus reducing suitable targets for detection)¹⁰⁵ or by flooding the host with antigens to induce host tolerance to tumor markers¹⁰⁶.

An alternative to engineering immune cells to attack cancer is to edit the programming of cancer cells themselves. Advancements in nano-scale delivery tools like lipid nanoparticles (Figure 3) make it possible to deliver genetic material to host cells that restore gene activity in target cancer cells. The tumor suppressor p53 is one of the most frequently mutated proteins in cancer and is known to be activated by “oncogenic signaling” from other proteins. Ras and Src are two families of oncogenic proteins that promote cellular replication. In healthy cells, p53 responds to hyperactive signaling from Ras and Src by suppressing the cell cycle or promoting cell death through Apoptosis (Figure 4), but when p53 is mutated, it may no longer respond to oncogenic activity. Therefore, some therapies in development aim to restore p53 activity by delivering healthy mRNA p53 (wt-p53) transcripts to cancer cells via lipid nano-particles and injection^{107,108}.

While p53 is not necessarily implicated in all cancers, it may still be possible to use this approach across a broad range of cancer subtypes. If the protein folding problem has a deterministic computable solution, then it should be possible to selectively activate p53 in only those cells that are cancerous. By designing a novel protein that only activates p53 in the presence of an oncogenic protein, it may be possible to selectively target cancer cells without relying on MHC peptide presentation, which is frequently deactivated in cancer¹⁰⁹. The theoretical designer protein Transducer of Oncogenic Signaling (TOS) recognizes mutant oncogenic protein structures and selectively activates p53 in their presence. While TOS can in principle be developed with modern technology, it would potentially require each case of cancer to be given a unique TOS protein to target a unique oncogenic structure. This would still offer another strategy for treating cancer, but the fundamental problem of protein recognition never really goes away.

While LNP-mediated RNA therapy may provide a viable alternative to CAR-T therapy, according to these results, the only certainty is that both treatments will fail for some cancer cases. This is because both approaches fundamentally rely on protein recognition to target cancer cells. If some protein structures are uncomputable by machines and unrecognizable by cells, then it follows that all such interventions will fail for some cancer cases. In the case of TOS induced p53 mediated apoptosis, the dependency is on TOS to respond to the activity of oncogenic proteins, while the protein targets of CAR-T therapy are tumor antigens present on the surface of cancer cells. So in either case, identifying cancer cells correctly is dependent on being able to recognize the proteins they express.

Recommendations for Structure Prediction

The understanding that some protein structures are uncomputable helps explain some shortcomings of AlphaFold and offers two recommendations for improved structure prediction. Intrinsically disordered proteins like p53 have dozens of post-translational modifications^{71,110} and when coupled with diverse binding interactions, the actual structure of such proteins depends on not just current interactions, but

previous protein interactions too. Therefore, the first recommendation is to include a motif-aware model to infer structures using recognizable features such as binding motifs, post-translational modifications, and trafficking signals. Protein-protein interactions are complex enough that proteins can form computational systems with variable structures, and minimotifs are the fundamental components of those interactions. Additionally, they are not just important for flexible structures; even globular proteins may be completely covered in minimotifs, and failure to correctly identify sites of phosphorylation or proteolytic cleavage means failing to predict real-world interactions for proteins that are activated by post-translational modifications. Therefore, a motif-aware model will be necessary to understand the diverse and transient real-life behavior of proteins.

These results also help explain why AlphaFold and other homology models struggle to predict the impact of amino-acid substitutions on protein structure. Protein domains may consist of hundreds of amino acids, and a single substitution can potentially disrupt even large structures, but homology models tend to ignore these substitutions and predict a structure consistent with the non-mutant protein. Homology models rely on solved structures to infer a probable structure and work because all proteins are implicitly related through ancestry, but if atypical structures contribute to degenerative diseases or parasite evasion, then homology modeling should not be expected to predict these structures unless efforts are made to experimentally resolve atypical structures for homology models to train with. Therefore, the second recommendation is to use experimental methods to determine crystal structures of atypical or random peptides for inclusion in model training data.

To be clear, it stands as a prediction that if protein structures are uncountable, there should be a preponderance of atypical structures and non-repeating crystal structures not observed in biological systems. Therefore, investment in experimental structures of peptide sequences that are randomly generated, or otherwise known to confound homology models, is recommended to understand the broader folding landscape of proteins.

Conclusion

Returning to the question of “can machines think?” – the question is not meaningless, but can be indirectly answered by denying that organisms can solve problems unsolvable by machines. If living organisms have any common tool that somehow goes beyond the constraints of classical Turing machines, then one would expect such a solution to be implemented to regulate the most fundamental cellular behaviors like protein folding and cellular replication.

The greater lesson from this analysis, however, is that computability plays a critical role in *complex biological processes* and has practical implications for *cancer therapy and protein structure prediction*. There are two high-level constraints imposed, however. First, different forms of cancer may have similar pathology, but they can have no universal solution. Second, the general protein folding problem is undecidable. That is, even if everything were known about the physical processes that govern protein structure, some protein structures would still be unpredictable.

Three recommendations follow naturally from this work. First, early intervention and combined genetic therapies will be necessary for the most subversive forms of cancer. Second, the fact that there are cardinally more protein structures than sequences suggests that homology models, including AlphaFold, are overfitted on biologically normative structures and investments in crystallizing atypical or possibly randomly generated peptide sequences to better understand the broader folding landscape is recommended. Finally, it may be beneficial to use available minimotif resources to build a model capable of better predicting protein structures that are informed by known binding motifs and post-translational modifications.

Supplemental Methods

Bijection of Natural Numbers to Polymers

In order to show that polymers can be used to represent natural numbers, it must be shown that polymers are bijective to natural numbers. A bijection is a 1-to-1 pairing between sets such that every element in either set has a corresponding unique partner in the other set. This holds for any kind of polymer that forms linear chains and has finite distinct monomers.

Two sets A and B are bijective if they are *one to one* and if A is *onto* B⁸⁰. That is:

Given:

$$F: A \rightarrow B; a, b \in A$$

The sets A and B are *one to one* if and only if ⁸⁰:

$$a \neq b \rightarrow F(a) \neq F(b), \text{ alternatively: } a = b \rightarrow F(a) = F(b)$$

The sets A and B are *onto* if and only if ⁸⁰:

$$F(a) = b$$

Let F be a function from RNA sequences to natural numbers to show that the set of DNA, RNA or peptide sequences is the same size as the set of natural numbers.

$$F(A) \equiv 1$$

$$F(C) \equiv 2$$

$$F(G) \equiv 3$$

$$F(U) \equiv 4$$

$$AAAA \Rightarrow A(4^3) + A(4^2) + A(4^1) + A(4^0) - 1$$

$$AAAA \Rightarrow 1(4^3) + 1(4^2) + 1(4^1) + 1(4^0) - 1$$

$$AAAA \Rightarrow 64 + 16 + 4 + 1 - 1 = 84$$

$$AGCU \Rightarrow A(4^3) + G(4^2) + C(4^1) + U(4^0) - 1$$

$$AGCU \Rightarrow 1(4^3) + 3(4^2) + 2(4^1) + 4(4^0) - 1$$

$$AGCU \Rightarrow (1 \times 64) + (3 \times 16) + (2 \times 4) + (4 \times 1) - 1 = 111$$

A similar arrangement can be made for protein peptide sequences.

Peano axioms for polymers

Linear polymers grow by linking monomers end-to-end, forming a molecular chain, and the successor function of the Peano Axioms is analogous to this process. This can be applied to any linear polymer provided one is committed to using only one monomer type. That is, this proof holds for DNA, RNA, and proteins but requires that any one of the four possible nucleotides be chosen and used exclusively for polymerization.

1. For any organic polymer, the absence of any polymers or monomers represents the number zero. The zero chain is simply taken to be the absence of monomers and represents 0.
2. Every chain has a successor polymer whose mass grows proportionally with chain length. If polymerization occurs through an elimination or substitution reaction, it is required that the reaction always yields the same products and that the mass of the polymer still grows linearly.
3. A chemical reaction is said to be an irreversible reaction if the reaction only proceeds in one direction and not in reverse¹¹. Polymerization is an irreversible reaction; therefore, the zero chain is the successor of no polymer.
4. If two polymers have the same mass, then they have the same successor.
5. Inductive Argument: Any property that is true of chains of length 0, n, and n+1 is true of polymers of any size.

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